

Potentiometric Study of the Complexes of Indium(III) with Some Azo Dyes

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Campus, NagpurManuscript received 21 September 1977, revised 3 February 1978,
accepted 14 March 1978

SPPECTROPHOTOMETRIC study of indium(III) complexes with 3-hydroxy-4-[(6-hydroxy-*m*-tolyl)azo]-1-naphthalene sulfonic acid (trivial name: Calmagite) (CLM), 3-hydroxy-4-[(2-hydroxy-naphthyl)azo]-1-naphthalene. Sulfonic acid (trivial name: Solochrome Dark Blue) (SDB), 4-(2-pyridylazo)-resorcinol (PAR) and 1-(2'-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) has been reported by different workers¹⁻⁸. However, the potentiometric study involving the stepwise formation of these complexes, has been reported for the first time in the present communication. The studies have been carried out with SDB and CLM in aqueous media. However, due to the low solubility of PAR and PAN in aqueous media the studies with these ligands have been made in 50% dioxan-water media. The "Practical" proton-ligand stability constants of the ligands and the metal-ligand stability constants (stepwise) have been obtained by Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{9,10} as used by Irving and Rossotti¹¹.

Experimental

Reagents: A stock solution (0.02 M) of $\text{In}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Schuchardt, Munchen) was prepared in calculated quantity of perchloric acid and the metal content was estimated as 8-hydroxy quinolate¹². The stock solutions (0.001M) of CLM (B.D.H.) and SDB (B.D.H.) were prepared in double distilled water. The stock solutions (0.005M) of PAR (B.D.H.) and PAN (E.Merck) were prepared in purified dioxan¹³. All these ligand solutions were standardised potentiometrically.

Solutions of carbon dioxide free 0.5M sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) and 0.5M perchloric acid (E. Merck) were prepared and were standardised potentiometrically. The stock solution (1.0M) of sodium perchlorate was prepared by dissolving AnalaR (Riedel) $\text{NaClO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in double distilled water.

A pH-meter (Beckman model H-2) with a glass-calomel electrode assembly was used to determine the change in hydrogen ion concentration of the solutions, using a KNO_3 salt bridge. A thermostat with resulting accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ$ was used.

Titration Procedure: Three mixtures were prepared containing acid, acid+ligand and acid+ligand+metal ion, such that the concentrations of common ingredients were identical in different cases. The ionic strength ($\mu=0.2M$) was maintained

by adding neutral sodium perchlorate. The ratio between the metal content and the ligand was kept at 1:5. The difference in the amount of sodium hydroxide utilised for the last two titrations was taken as a measure of the extent of complexation.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry:

For In(III)-SDB system it was observed that in the metal titration curve, four extra moles of NaOH were required in comparison to ligand titration curve before a steep rise was observed. This indicates that 1:2 complex formation takes place and there is liberation of protons during chelation, from the two hydroxy groups present at ortho position to azo group. Similar results have been observed for In(III)-CLM system, which is expected also because SDB differs from CLM only in the hydrocarbon residue.

For In(III)-PAR and In(III)-PAN systems it was observed that in comparison to ligand titration curve approximately 2 extra moles of NaOH were required before finally an inflection was observed in the metal titration curve indicating that 1:2 complex formation takes place and that there is liberation of protons during chelation from the hydroxy group present at the ortho position to azo group.

Proton-ligand stability constants:

The formation curves for the proton-ligand systems of CLM and SDB drawn between \bar{n}_A and pH were found to be extended between 0 and 2 in the \bar{n}_A scale, thus showing complete dissociation of $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group.

The formation curves for the proton-ligand systems of PAR and PAN drawn between \bar{n}_A and "pH-meter reading" were found to be extended between 0 and 3 for PAR and between 0 and 2 for PAN in the \bar{n}_A scale.

The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for CLM, SDB, PAR and PAN and $\log K_3$ for PAR obtained by the method of interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values having error limits ± 0.05 are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE-1

PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 25° AND $\mu=0.2$

Ligand	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_3$
SDB	12.87	7.01	-
CLM	12.15	8.23	-
PAR*	12.96	6.54	2.49
PAN*	12.17	1.96	-

* Experiments in 50% dioxan

Metal-ligand stability constants:

In case of SDB, CLM and PAR systems the reactants had intense colour at $\text{pH} \approx 7.0$, rather the solution showed opalescence and in case of In(III)-

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NOTES

PAN systems precipitation of the complex was observed at $pH \approx 5.0$. Hence, the portion of the titration curves above these pH values could not be used for obtaining the formation function \bar{n} . In order to obtain stability constants the formation curves were drawn between \bar{n} and pL . The approximate values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were obtained from the formation curves by reading them at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. The values were not considered to be reliable because $\log K_1/K_2 < 3.0$. Therefore, the values obtained have been further refined by least squares method. The values of stability constants are summarised in Table-2.

TABLE-2

METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 25° AND $\mu=0.2$

System	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
In(III)-SDB	16.48	14.66
In(III)-CLM	17.09	14.87
In(III)-PAR*	12.54	11.46
In(III)-PAN*	12.19	10.57

*Experiments in 50% dioxan

Among the azo dyes the order in the stability constant values was found to be $CLM > SDB > PAR > PAN$. But the values of $\log K_1/\beta^H$ showed that the complexing tendency of PAR and PAN for In(III) was more than that of CLM and SDB. This may be due to the presence of stronger complexing group for In(III), like pyridyl nitrogen in the former ligands.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. H. Sahasrabudhey, Head, Chemistry Department, Nagpur University, Nagpur, for providing necessary facilities and University Grants Commission for the award of a research fellowship to one of the authors (R.S.).

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Some Anionic Mixed-Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II)

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Manuscript received 2 November 1977, accepted 14 March 1978

THOUGH anionic complexes of cobalt(II) of the type $[CoX_4]^{-2}$, where X is halogen or pseudo-halogen have long been studied¹⁻⁵ in detail as typical tetrahedral compounds, little has been done to change the stereochemistry of these complexes by reacting with other nitrogen, oxygen or sulphur ligands. To increase the coordination number, particularly to synthesise compounds of coordination number five, we have been trying to synthesise anionic mixed-ligand complexes starting from these type of tetrahedral compounds. In this communication, we report a number of tetra-, penta- and hexacoordinated mixed-ligand (thiocyanate) complexes, using different ligand donor atoms.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. An ethanolic solution of cobalt thiocyanate was treated with an ethanolic solution of tetramethylammonium thiocyanate in 1 : 2 proportion when blue crystalline compound of ditetramethylammonium tetrathiocyanato cobalt(II) was separated out. This was then filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuo.

The mixed-ligand complexes were prepared, by adding requisite amount (1 : 2 ratio) of ligands separately to ethanolic suspension of ditetramethylammonium tetrathiocyanato cobalt(II) and refluxing for about 30 minutes. On cooling crystalline compounds were separated out which were then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuo.

Metal and thiocyanate in the complexes were determined by complexometric E.D.T.A. method and nitrogen by micro analysis. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone medium using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurement were made over solid specimens by Gouy method. IR spectra were recorded on KBr phase using Perkin-Elmer-221 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded using M/100 (chloroform base) solution by Hilger-Watt U. V. Speck spectrophotometer. Relevant analytical, conductance and magnetic susceptibility and spectral data are given in Table 1.